

Nuclear options

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Fractional charges for Quarks were first proposed during a chat between Robert Serber and Murray Gell-Mann in 1963 [1]; upon hearing about a threesome of particles comprising Nucleons, Gell-Mann 'after a couple of minutes of thought and scribbling, came up with the fractional charges'.

We'll never know what the scribbling was, but linear algebra makes it plain. The charge vector for Nucleons (Proton/Neutron) is clearly

$$N = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

while the content matrix [2] is

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$$

so the constituent Quark charge vector

$$Q = \begin{pmatrix} q1 \\ q2 \end{pmatrix}$$

must satisfy

$$C Q = N$$

hence

$$Q = C^{-1}N$$

or in components

$$\begin{pmatrix} q1 \\ q2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 2/3 & -1/3 \\ -1/3 & 2/3 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 2/3 \\ -1/3 \end{pmatrix}$$

and the fractional charges emerge algebraically; no magic here.

Collision experiments over the decades have amply confirmed Quark presence within Nucleons; but no charge measurements has ever yielded fractional outcomes.

Now, the highlighted equation above is also satisfied by the signed charge vector

$$\text{sign}(Q) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

with the content matrix is

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 2 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$$

But this would alter fundamentally the nature of Neutrons: they must be **TetraQuarks**. The charge makeup of such Nucleons/AntiNucleons would be

$$\text{Proton} = \{\oplus, \ominus, \oplus\} \quad \text{AntiProton} = \{\ominus, \oplus, \ominus\}$$

$$\text{Neutron} = \{\oplus, \ominus, \oplus, \ominus\} \quad \text{AntiNeutron} = \{\ominus, \oplus, \ominus, \oplus\}$$

Now, Quarks termed Up(**u**) and Down(**d**) makeup Nucleons as

$$\text{Proton} = \{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{d}, \mathbf{u}\}$$

$$\text{Neutron} = \{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}\}$$

and from the algebra above, their charges are (inherently)

$$q_1 = q(\mathbf{u}) = 2/3$$

$$q_2 = q(\mathbf{d}) = -1/3$$

The startling fascination with fractionation would vanish if the **Up** and **Down** Quarks had **Positrons** and **Electrons** respectively embedded, inheriting effortlessly their signed charges.

In classical Beta-decay [3], a free Neutron decays into a Proton+Electron+Neutrino. In terms of charges, this is

$$\text{Neutron} = \{\oplus, \ominus, \ominus\} \Rightarrow \text{Proton} = \{\oplus, \ominus, \oplus\} + \text{Electron} = \{\ominus\}$$

involving a (mysterious) charge transformation $\{\ominus\} \Rightarrow \{\oplus\}$ after decay, offset by the emitted $\{\ominus\}$ for charge conservation. The signed-charge model implies Beta-decay works as

$$\text{Neutron} = \{\oplus, \ominus, \oplus, \ominus\} \Rightarrow \text{Proton} = \{\oplus, \ominus, \oplus\} + \text{Electron} = \{\ominus\}$$

making charge bookkeeping more transparent. Similarly (though more ephemerally)

$$\text{AntiNeutron} = \{\ominus, \oplus, \ominus, \oplus\} \Rightarrow \text{AntiProton} = \{\ominus, \oplus, \ominus\} + \text{Positron} = \{\oplus\}$$

for AntiNeutron decay.

Of course, there is no experimental evidence that Neutrons are TetraQuarks, let alone that Electrons or Positrons are embedded in Nucleons, attached to their respective constituent hosts. Also, BiQuark Mesons with non-zero charge end up having twice the charge using the signed-Quark model, contrary to observations.

Still, free Proton decay is a 'once in a 10^{34} years' event, meaning its (hypothetical) Positrons are held tightly. Thus the enormous imbalance of Electron vs. Positron population presence in Nature would be accounted for: **Nucleons have Positrons trapped!**

References

[1] George Zweig: "Discovering Quarks", Cambridge University Press, 2025, p. 79.

[2] 'Quark matrices': <https://zenodo.org/records/18303155>

[3] Wikipedia article on 'Beta Decay'.